

7 Appendices

Appendix A: Identifying Shifts

A.1 Linear Regression

A.1.1 Stable Gradient

A1.2 Varying Gradient

A.2 Hidden Markov Modelling

Appendix B: Model Evaluation

B.1 Coverage Testing

B.1.1 Coverage test scatter plots

B.1.2 Distance to perfect point boxplot for each model (full sample of run tests)

B.1.3 Spatial variation in coverage test model performance

B.2 Split Sample Testing

B.2.1 Performance over dry period for each model (full sample of run tests)

B.3 Evaluation

B.3.1 Future Climate Projections

Due to timing of running LASCAM, the sample size presented below is limited to 70.

B.3.2 Hydrograph of Driest Year

- - - LASCAM (Weighted Split Trotter Calibration) - - - GR4J (NSE Calibration) - - - GR4J SGW Intra (Weighted Split Trotter Calibration) — Observed — Precipitation
 Time (days)